

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

IMPROVING THE RELIABILITY OF PROTECTION AGAINST SHORT-CIRCUIT CURRENTS BY ELIMINATING INTERFERENCE IN THE FORM OF STARTING CURRENTS OF ELECTRIC MOTORS

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ABSTRACT

The problem of increasing the reliability of protecting low-voltage electrical networks from short-circuit currents by creating a new function in the releases of automatic switches - blocking protection when starting electric motors is considered. Identification of the starting mode is based on the use of the properties of the power function of the electrical circuit - the time dependence of the sum of the squares of the instantaneous values of the currents of the three-phase circuit. This makes it possible to reliably (in parallel by two methods) determine the value $\text{COS } \varphi$ of the mode of the protected circuit. Blocking of protection at start-up of electric motors allows you to significantly reduce the current settings of the circuit breakers in order to ensure both, the protection of the backup of the downstream circuit breaker by the superior one, and the protection of long lines from remote short circuit currents.

Keywords: power function, inrush currents, short circuit protection.

Starting currents of electric motors (EM) in the system of protection of electrical networks against short-circuit currents (SC) are harmful interference and prevent the implementation of the protection of the redundancy of failures of downstream circuit breakers by the upstream ones. In particular, starting currents do not allow the upstream circuit breaker to reduce the current settings to the level at which it can and should operate in the event of a feeder circuit breaker failure. In some cases, the starting current of an EM located near the current source may be greater than the remote short circuit current at the end of a long line. Therefore, in order to avoid false protection trips during EM start-ups, it is necessary to choose a current setting greater than the value of the expected remote short circuit current.

Thus, in order to increase the reliability of protection against short-circuit currents, it is necessary

$$i_a(t) = I_m \left[\sin(\omega t + \psi - \varphi + 2\pi/3) - \sin(\psi - \varphi + 2\pi/3)e^{-t/\tau} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$i_b(t) = I_m \left[\sin(\omega t + \psi - \varphi) - \sin(\psi - \varphi)e^{-t/\tau} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$i_c(t) = I_m \left[\sin(\omega t + \psi - \varphi - 2\pi/3) - \sin(\psi - \varphi - 2\pi/3)e^{-t/\tau} \right] \quad (3),$$

where: I_m - the amplitude value of the current, φ - the angle of shift between the current and the EMF, ψ - the angle corresponding to the moment of occurrence of the perturbation current.

As can be seen from the above dependences, the nature of the change in the current in the transient mode depends not only on $\text{COS } \varphi$ (or τ), but also on the moment of occurrence of the perturbation current - the angle ψ . This is due to the fact that the values $\text{COS } \varphi$ of the currents in the steady state are not constant values, but change according to their own laws. Therefore, in order to reliably determine the value, a three-phase circuit parameter is required, the value of which is constant in the steady state.

to rebuild it from the starting currents of the electric motor, for which it is advisable to "monitor" the power factor - $\text{COS } \varphi$

It is known that in the start mode of the EM the values $\text{COS } \varphi = (0,2 \div 0,3)$ are, while in the short circuit mode in the line $\text{COS } \varphi = (0,7 \div 0,8)$. At the same time, for reliable identification of the starting mode, the value $\text{COS } \varphi$ must be determined quickly enough, while the EM rotor is still stationary, because as the rotor spins up, the value $\text{COS } \varphi$ changes upwards.

The transient process of changing the instantaneous values of phase currents is determined by the following well-known expressions:

In a three-phase current system, if we consider it as a whole - from generation, transmission, and consumption, the force on the generator shaft is constant in magnitude. Then, this effort is divided into three, variable in magnitude, components, but in the receiver, the sum of these efforts must remain a constant value. Therefore, the sum of the electrodynamic forces of all three phases at the consumer will be a constant value. Since these efforts are proportional to the square of the current, then the dependence of the change in time of the sum of the squares of the values of the currents, denoted as a force function, will be constant in magnitude.

The analytical expression of the force function $F(t)$ has the following form:

$$F(t) = [i_a(t)]^2 + [i_b(t)]^2 + [i_c(t)]^2 \quad (4)$$

where I_f is the effective value of the current in the phases.

Substituting (1), (2), (3) into (4) we get:

$$F(t) = 3I_f^2(1 - 2e^{-t/\tau} \cos \omega t + e^{-2t/\tau}) \quad (5)$$

Fig.1 Graphs of the power function for different values of $\cos \varphi$

From (5), it follows that the force function has a remarkable property - it does not depend on the moment of occurrence of the perturbation current (angle ψ) and is determined only by the value $\cos \varphi$ (or τ) of the circuit. In Fig.1. Graphs $F(t)$ are given for different

values of $\cos \varphi$. We see that the force function curve changes over time from its maximum value $F_{\max}$ to its minimum value $F_{\min}$. At the same time, the smaller the $\cos \varphi$, then greater is the ratio of these extremes.

Fig.2 Dependence of the value of $\cos \varphi$ on the value of the coefficient K_F

Figure 2 shows a graphical dependence of $\cos \varphi$ on the coefficient, - $K_F = F_{\max}/F_{\min}$. It clearly shows that the coefficient K_F is a sufficiently informative parameter to determine $\cos \varphi$ of the circuit with a disturbance current and, ultimately, to identify the mode of the protected circuit (when starting the EM - $K_F = 2,8$, and when short circuit - $K_F = 1,2$).

You can also determine $\cos \varphi$ of the circuits using the "online" calculation of the shock current coefficient K_y . (K_y is the multiplicity of the shock short-circuit current relative to the steady-state value I_v).

The calculated dependences K_y on the value $\cos \varphi$ (or τ) are given in the technical literature [1] and [2] correspond to the most severe case, when the moment of occurrence of the perturbation current (angle ψ) coincides with the moment when the EMF curve in one of the phases passes through zero. In reality, it is not always possible to determine K_y based on the actual values of the phase current curves (1), (2), (3), due to the random nature of the angle ψ .

However, with the power function, the actual value K_y is successfully calculated. Examining it for an extremum shows that K_y it is equal to $3I_y^2$,

regardless of the angle ψ . Thus, in the "online" calculation, we first determine the value I_y .

$$I_y = \sqrt{F_{\max}/3} \quad (6)$$

The steady state value I_v of the current can be obtained in the usual way - by measuring the current at the end of the transient. But I_v the current can be determined much faster. As can be seen from Fig. 1, the value of the force function corresponding to the moment of time $t=16\text{ms}$ from the beginning of the occurrence of the perturbation current, for any values $\text{COS } \varphi$, is equal to the steady value of the force function, namely $F_{16} = 3I_v^2$. Then the surge current coefficient can be found from the following expression:

$$K_y = \sqrt{F_{\max}/F_{16}} \quad (7)$$

Determining the value of $\text{COS } \varphi$ in parallel by two methods significantly increases the reliability of the identification of the starting mode of the ED.

The algorithm "online" - calculations for the identification of the starting mode of the EM based on the processing of the power function, is shown in Fig.3.

Separate mathematical and logical operations are presented in the form of modules. In module 1, information about Δi_j the excitation current is extracted from the output signal of the current sensors.

To do this, the corresponding discrete values of the current of the previous period are subtracted from the current discrete values i_{jp} of the phase currents. In module 2, the instantaneous values F_j of the force function are determined, and in module 3, the force function is formed $F(t)$ and its extreme values $F_{\max}$ and $F_{\min}$ are determined, as well as the value of F_{16} . In module 4, the value of the coefficient $K_F = F_{\max}/F_{\min}$ is determined, and in module 5, the value of $\text{COS } \varphi_2$ is determined from the dependence $\text{COS } \varphi = f(K_F)$. In module 6, the value K_y of the surge current coefficient is determined from the expression $K_y = \sqrt{F_{\max}/F_{16}}$. In module 7, the value $\text{COS } \varphi_1$ is determined from the dependence $\text{COS } \varphi = f(K_y)$. In module 8, the effective value $I_v = 1/3\sqrt{F_{16}}$ of the circuit perturbation current is determined and compared with the value $7I_r$, where I_r is the operating current of the circuit. If the condition is met $I_v \leq 7I_r$, then in block 8 the signal "Yes" is generated..

Fig.3 Algorithm for implementing the function of blocking the operation of protection against starting currents of electric motors

In module 9, the value $\text{COS } \varphi_2$ is compared with the allowable value, and if the inequality is met $\text{COS } \varphi_2 \leq 0,5$, a "Yes" signal is generated. In module 10, the value $\text{COS } \varphi_1$ is compared with a valid value,

and if the inequality is met $\text{COS } \varphi_1 \leq 0,5$, a "Yes" signal is generated. In the logical module 11, upon receipt of three "Yes" commands, a protection blocking signal is generated.

The introduction of the function of blocking protection at the start of an EM into automatic switches

radically changes the approach to building protection of branched electrical networks from short-circuit currents. Indeed, in the absence of interference in the form of starting currents of the EM, the current settings in the switches I_S at different stages of protection can be set significantly lower than the values of the starting currents, namely: not $(5 \div 7)$ times the operating current of the circuit I_r , but only $(2 \div 3) I_r$.

With the specified reduced current setting in the feeder circuit breaker, the problem of protecting long lines from remote short-circuit currents is solved. A similar decrease in current settings in the introductory circuit breakers, in most cases, allows solving the problem of redundancy with their help of failures of downstream feeder circuit breakers. It is known that with redundancy, the probability of failure-free operation of any technical systems increases significantly. In this regard, the protection of electrical networks from currents, when eliminating interference in the form of inrush currents of the ED, becomes much more reliable.

Summary. The reliability of protection of electric networks can be significantly increased if unwanted interference in the form of starting currents of electric motors is eliminated. To implement the blocking function, a method is proposed for quick and reliable identification of the starting mode using the power function of the current. The introduction of the blocking function of protection when starting electric motors into the circuit breaker releases allows you to build protection systems in a new way, providing both, the redundancy of circuit breaker failures and protection of long lines from remote currents short circuits.

References

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